

SHORT NOTES

Use of Cation-exchange Resin for Total Anion Analysis of Aqueous Solutions Containing Beryllium(II) Ion

R. P. Bhatnagar, R. C. Arora, and B. G. Mahajan

Though the ion-exchange methods have been employed extensively for determination of the total salt concentration in aqueous solution, using cation exchangers in hydrogen forms¹, similar studies with less-familiar elements are only a few. Recently total anion analysis in solution, containing uranyl ion, has been reported by Day *et al*². In the present work, Be²⁺ ion has been used to investigate the possibilities of total anion analysis in its presence by cation exchangers in H-form.

Procedure.—The analysis was carried out by column technique, using a pyrex glass column (50×1.0 cm) with removable perforated disc at the lower end and a ground-glass lower end to fit in B12 Quickfit joint of an adapter. Resin, Amberlite IR-120(H) or IR-112(H) was filled in it in the fully swollen condition as a water slurry to provide a column of 18 cm after setting.

Samples for analysis were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of beryllium hydroxide (prepared from B.D.H. AnalaR beryllium nitrate solution by precipitating it as hydroxide with a KOH solution, collecting the washed precipitate, and drying it) in measured volumes of standardised acid solution containing the anion under study. After appropriate dilution these were passed through the exchange column at the flow rate of 2ml/cm²/min. The influent volume was always kept at 20 ml. The column was then washed with double distilled water (at a much faster flow rate) to make it free of the acid generated due to exchange of the cation. The effluents with washings were collected carefully and titrated with a standardised NaOH solution to phenolphthalein end point. The titre values represent the total acid content and hence are used to calculate the total concentrations of anions.

Samples analysed in this way contained mole-equivalent ratios of anion to beryllium, as recorded in Table I. The time for analysis per sample was about 15 to 20 min. for all steps (*i.e.*, exchange, washing, and titration). The results of these analysis were satisfactory and were not influenced by the variation of the cation/acid ratio. The average percentage deviations in the results are recorded in Table I.

A similar method was used for the total cation concentration of beryllium salt solutions using Amberlite IR-120 (H). The solutions of beryllium sulphate and beryllium

1. Samuelson, "Ion Exchangers in Analytical Chemistry", John Wiley and Sons Inc., N. Y., 1953.

2. *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 611.

chloride were used for the purpose of analysis. The exchange of beryllium ion on H-form of the resin afforded equivalent quantities of acids in effluents, which were titrated with standard alkali solutions to phenolphthalein end point. Titre values corresponded to the total anion concentration in the solutions from which the cation concentration was calculated. The results for beryllium, found by ion-exchange method, are within $\pm 0.8\%$ error.

TABLE I

Anion added.	Amberlite IR-120 (H)		Amberlite IR-112 (H)	
	Mole-eq. ratio of anion/Be ²⁺ .	*Average % deviation.	Mole-eq. ratio of anion/Be ²⁺ .	*Average % deviation.
Sulphate	2.20 to 3.57	± 0.65	3.21 to 16.25	± 0.19
Chloride	1.39 to 2.14	± 0.34	1.03 to 2.42	± 0.50
Nitrate	1.40 to 2.21	± 0.23	1.44 to 3.03	± 0.37
Perchlorate	1.20 to 2.00	± 0.17	0.97 to 1.93	± 0.58
		Av. ± 0.35		Av. ± 0.39

*These are average deviations of 5 readings obtained with changed mole-equivalent ratios.

The results indicate that anion analysis of solutions containing Be²⁺ can be carried out with great accuracy and rapidity. The average deviations of the results for anion found to the actual amount present in the two resins used were ± 0.35 and ± 0.39 . Similarly for cation analysis, these were quite satisfactory. As the beryllium salt samples, particularly nitrate and chloride, are supplied in solution forms, their exact concentration can be obtained very quickly by this process. Also in case of solutions, which are prepared by dissolving the oxide or the hydroxide of beryllium, the estimation for total anion concentration can be made by acidimetry without any complications.